

SCURVY IN A CHILD TEN MONTHS OLD.

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The Medical Times and Gazette 1873;I(March 8):248.

The volume is available at:

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=mdp.39015023943791&seq=256>

<https://archive.org/details/s3591id1378475/page/248/mode/2up>

Additional note on the case on p.322:

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=mdp.39015023943791&seq=330>

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This is one of the very early reports of infant scurvy.

Background, see eg.

<https://zenodo.org/records/15343353> LE Holt

<https://zenodo.org/records/15342857> GF Still

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1975442> GF Still

<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/40505> pp.1-22. AF Hess

EDWIN R., aged 10 months, was brought to the Dispensary on Tuesday, January 7, 1873. The mother states that she only suckled the child for three weeks, when her milk entirely left her. She then fed it upon condensed milk and water, allowing it two tins of milk weekly until it was six months old. Up to this time it did well, and got fat. When the infant had passed the sixth month she fed it upon Chapman's entire wheat flour, condensed milk, and water, giving it six teaspoonfuls of the flour, with three of the milk, together with water, in the twenty-four hours. For two months after using this diet nothing was noticed, but since then she says it has been gradually wasting. Three weeks before coming to the Dispensary she observed the child cried very much upon its knees and ankles being moved, and that its gums were swollen and bled very easily. Finding it got worse she brought it here, when it was found to present the following appearances:— The trunk and limbs generally wasted, with sallow-coloured skin; on both legs were small petechiæ, which did not disappear upon pressure; upon looking into the mouth the gums on the upper jaw were found to be in a spongy condition, bleeding readily upon being touched; teeth, of which six were cut, not loose; tongue clean, and breath not offensive. The child was quiet and sleepy, but cried immediately upon its ankles or knees being moved, which appeared swollen. The mother also says lately it has had diarrhœa, but she has not seen any blood in the motions. It was ordered—R. Syr. ferri iodid. mxv., ol. morrhuæ zj. 4tis horis; also to drink plenty of cow's milk, and a little lemon-juice.

January 14.—Gums have resumed their normal state; petechiæ have entirely disappeared; there is no pain upon moving the ankles or knees, and the child appears quite cheerful.

Remarks.— One peculiar feature in this case is the early age in which the disease appeared. On referring to Copland's "Dictionary of Medicine" I find it is stated that scurvy may occur at any age from childhood upwards; and again, Billroth, in his "Surgical Pathology," says that this disease is very common in children; but I cannot find any case mentioned in which the patient was so young as the above. What was the cause of it in this instance? Dr. Aitken, in his "Practice of Medicine" (vol. ii., page 74), gives the causes of scurvy as follows:—"1. Deficiency of absolute nourishment. 2. Improper adjudication of the nutrient and respiratory principles of the diet; its monotony. 3. Bad quality of the diet; improper cooking, or none at all. 4. Exposure to cold, combined with imperfect clothing and labour beyond the strength of the best-fed men. 5. The persistent pernicious influence of residence in a paludal¹ district." For the first six months, according to the mother's statement, the child was fed upon condensed milk and water alone, and did well; so I do not think that the cause can be put down to this diet, but rather to what followed, and then not so much to the diet given as to the short supply of it. Three teaspoonfuls of condensed milk together with six of the flour in the twenty-four hours would certainly not be sufficient for a child of that tender age; and yet the mother expressed her belief to me that the disease was due to over-feeding! In a week the child was free from the disease; but I fully believe the result is to be attributed to the good supply of cow's milk rather than to the lemon-juice or the iron, although they all may have had their share in the cure.

1 Marsh, wetlands
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Paludal>